

Generating Cisgenic Sexing Strains in Insect Pests

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Article

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Additional Declarations:

Yes there is potential Competing Interest. A patent has been filed on this technology. O.S.A is a founder of Agragene, Inc. and Synvect, Inc. with equity interest. N.P.K is a founder of Synvect, Inc. with equity interest. The terms of this arrangement have been reviewed and approved by the University of California, San Diego in accordance with its conflict-of-interest policies. All other authors declare no competing interests.

Table 1 is available in the Supplementary Files section.

Generating Cisgenic Sexing Strains in Insect Pests

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36 **Abstract**

37 Insect pest population control via sterile insect technique severely benefits from separation by sex
38 prior to release. To simplify this process, traditional genetics has been deployed to develop
39 genetic sexing strains (GSSs) for several disease vectors and agricultural pests of vast economic
40 significance, although very few are applied in the field due to associated fitness costs and
41 instability. In this study, we generated a method to engineer cisgenic GSS (CGSS) in insects. We
42 use CRISPR/Cas9-mediated homology-directed repair to seamlessly translocate a sex-specific
43 alternatively spliced intron into a dominant phenotypic gene generating a genetically stable strain
44 that enables sex-sorting by eye. To achieve this feat, we use *Ceratitis capitata* as our model and
45 relied on the sex-specifically spliced intron of the endogenous *transformer* gene, which we
46 seamlessly inserted into the pupal colouration *white pupae* gene. This minimal modification
47 resulted in the generation of a homozygous strain we term IMPERIAL that was phenotypically
48 stable where all female pupae are brown while male pupae are white with overall good fitness.
49 By minimally editing the genome, our CGSS approach can be applied to other pests that may aid
50 more efficient and economically suitable pest control.

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52 **Key words:** CRISPR/Cas9; Sex Specific Alternative Splicing; Genetic Sexing Strains, Medfly

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70 **Main text**

71 Genetic sexing strains (GSSs) have been developed in multiple insect species of economic
72 significance to allow easier male and female separation necessary for efficient population control.
73 Specifically, GSSs are used within sterile insect technique (SIT) programmes which work via
74 frequent releases of sterilised insects into the wild for temporary population control (1-3). Male-
75 only releases, aided by GSS implementation, strongly succour in released fly dispersal and their
76 mating frequency with wild females, thus enhancing SIT success (4-6). Vast efforts have focused
77 on GSS generation in mosquito disease vectors and agricultural fruit fly pests to avoid labour-
78 intensive sex-sorting by eliminating the females from the released population early in the life cycle
79 (7-12).

80

81 The traditional GSS approach requires two key attributes: a selectable marker and a Y-
82 chromosome or male-determining locus linkage from which it needs to be expressed (4). A
83 primary example of a traditional GSS is the VIENNA 8 strain developed in the tephritid fruit fly
84 pest *Ceratitidis capitata* (Mediterranean fruit fly or medfly) possessing an increasing threat to the
85 agricultural industry with its expanding global distribution and vast host range (13-14). VIENNA 8,
86 similarly to its predecessor VIENNA 7, relies on a radiation-induced simultaneous translocation
87 of *wp* gene and *temperature sensitive lethal (tsl)* genes onto the Y-chromosome involved in pupal
88 colouration and heat tolerance respectively (15-16). Whilst the former, *wp*, has been
89 characterised in multiple tephritids, the latter, *tsl*, remains to be identified in *C. capitata* and its
90 relatives. As the VIENNA 8 strain has a *wp* and *tsl* double-mutant background, the white-pupaed
91 females die upon embryonic heat exposure, whilst the brown-pupaed males persevere into
92 adulthood (4; 17). Across the *Tephritidae* family, such traditional GSSs have been successfully
93 developed in multiple species, although only those developed in *C. capitata* and *Anastrepha*
94 *ludens* have been implemented on a SIT facility scale (18-19). Other traditional examples tested
95 on a larger scale include the eye colour phenotype-dependent *Aedes aegypti* GSSs (20).

96

97 In parallel to similar GSSs in other tephritid species, the VIENNA 8 strain is infrequently
98 susceptible to phenotype loss via recombination requiring an extra filtering step at SIT facilities
99 (4, 21). Furthermore, they have notable reductions in fertility, thus creating obstacles for mass
100 rearing (18, 22). To elevate GSS fitness, multiple transgenic approaches have been engineered
101 for female exclusion either through a selectable phenotypic marker or female-specific lethality in
102 the medfly and other fruit fly species (23-33). Abundantly, a sex-specific intron from the
103 *transformer (tra)* gene has been implemented in the medfly for female-specific transgene

104 expression from the autosomes (25-26, 30). Most recently this was completed for female-specific
105 fluorescence marker expression in a Sexing Element Produced by Alternative RNA-splicing of
106 Transgenic Observable reporter (SEPARATOR) system whereby both the *C. capitata* and newly
107 the *A. ludens tra* introns were used (25). While these transgene-based approaches provide
108 exciting alternatives, they still require regulatory authorisation which can be a slow and
109 cumbersome process.

110
111 Herein, we wanted to develop a universal method in insects to engineer GSSs that use modern
112 engineering techniques to generate minimal genetic modifications wherein both donor and
113 recipient are derived from the same species which we call Cisgenic GSS (CGSS). We used the
114 medfly as our model system to engineer a non-transgenic CGSS without exogenous elements.
115 Sex-specific expression of the *wp* selectable marker was achieved through sex-specific splicing
116 of the *tra* intron. This was attained through a homology-directed repair (HDR)-dependent knock-
117 in of the *tra* intron seamlessly into the *white pupae (wp)* locus of wild-type Benakeion medfly
118 embryos, feasible due to recent success of CRISPR/Cas9-mediated HDR in the species (34-36).

119
120 Collectively, using the intron of *tra*, a master gene of tephritid female sex determination (37-39),
121 results in extremely robust desired phenotypes, rendering it suitable for further use in CGSSs, yet
122 to be developed. The knock-in construct (1167A) was engineered using the endogenous
123 *transformer (tra)* intron, which was placed between the homology arms of each approximately
124 700 bp in length. The anticipated outcome was female-specific *wp* gene expression, whereby
125 males harbouring two copies of the *tra*-containing *wp* gene would have a white pupae phenotype
126 and females harbouring two copies of the *tra*-containing *wp* gene would have a brown pupae
127 phenotype, which can be distinguished by eye (Fig. 1A). As the *wp* mutation is recessive in nature,
128 the knock-in strain, hereupon named IMPERIAL, was isolated using backcrosses to the
129 irradiation-generated *white pupae* knock-out (*wp*^{-/-}) strain at G0 and G1 (Fig. 1B). We confirmed
130 successful knock-in of the *tra* intron (*wp*^{KI+/-}) in all obtained brown-pupaed G2 females using
131 amplicon sequencing of the integration site. A homozygous *wp*^{KI+/+} line was established at G7 (F0)
132 after crossing sibling white-pupaed males with brown-pupaed females, genotyping all parents and
133 screening the whole progeny at every intermediate generation. To verify the integration in the
134 *wp*^{KI+/+} IMPERIAL strain, genomic DNA from CGSS females was sequenced. The sequencing
135 revealed reads with the expected 1345 bp CRISPR-HDR insertion indicating a seamless
136 intragenic insertion of the *tra* intron into the *wp* gene (fig. S1).

137

138 To verify the sex-sorting suitability of the strain, phenotypic pupae colour stability and sex ratios
139 of the IMPERIAL strain were examined alongside the existing VIENNA 8 GSS, where males and
140 females emerge from brown and white pupae accordingly. For five consecutive generations (F2-
141 F6), pupae and adult phenotypes were recorded for IMPERIAL (pupae n = 4147; adult n = 4074)
142 and VIENNA 8 (pupae n = 1386; adult n = 1227) strains in parallel, maintained under the same
143 conditions. As anticipated, in the $wp^{KI/+}$ IMPERIAL strain all females emerged from brown pupae
144 and all males emerged from white pupae (Fig. 2A). The reverse phenotypes were universally
145 observed amongst individuals from the VIENNA 8 strain. Altogether, the proportion of adult
146 females in the IMPERIAL strain (mean = 49.8%) exceeded that of the VIENNA 8 strain (mean =
147 37.4%). Whilst populations within every generation of the IMPERIAL strain adhered to the
148 expected 1:1 male: female sex ratio (chi-square goodness of fit tests), the VIENNA 8 did not at
149 F2, F4 and F5 (Fig. 2A). In sum these results confirm the phenotypic stability of the IMPERIAL
150 strain that, dissimilarly to VIENNA 8, consistently confines to the expected 1:1 male: female sex
151 ratio.

152

153 To better understand differences in the *tra* intron-dependent *wp* splicing in males and females of
154 the $wp^{KI/+}$ IMPERIAL strain, we performed reverse-transcription PCR (RT-PCR) on genomic and
155 complementary DNA (cDNA) templates from adult flies (fig. S2). A single female band was
156 amplified from the cDNA template, corresponding to a transcript with the fully spliced-out *tra* intron
157 (37), confirmed by sequencing thereafter. Male cDNA banding entirely consisted of larger
158 fragments from which two unique male isoforms with premature stop codons were isolated via
159 clonal sequencing, both containing sequences of the two male-specific exons. These results are
160 suggestive of functional White pupae protein production in females and ablation of its translation
161 in males. Further investigation into *wp* splicing of the IMPERIAL strain was conducted using
162 RNAseq. As expected, all three female libraries had multiple reads that spanned the junction
163 splicing the *tra* intron. In contrast, the three male libraries had no such reads indicating that the
164 intron is spliced in females and not in males (fig. S3). As expected, the clustering and principal
165 component analyses indicated a close relationship of samples by sex (fig. S4).

166

167 The IMPERIAL sexing strain was further compared to its parental wild-type Benakeion and
168 VIENNA 8 strains in terms of general fitness, and thus suitability for larger-scale employment.
169 First, a standard egg-adult survival assay utilising triplicate sibling crosses of 10 males with 20
170 females was conducted, whereby rates of egg laying, egg hatching, hatched larvae-pupae
171 recovery, pupae-adult recovery, and total egg-adult recovery were assessed (Fig. 2B). Kruskal-

172 Wallis and sequential Dunn's tests were performed as means of statistical analysis. Notably, egg
173 production within the measured time period was significantly elevated in the IMPERIAL strain
174 compared to both wild-type and VIENNA 8 strains ($p < 0.05^*$). Hatching rate in VIENNA 8 was
175 significantly lower than in wild-type ($p = 0.0036^{**}$), although insignificant reductions in the
176 IMPERIAL strain were also observed ($p = 0.0899$). We recorded the highest larval-pupal survival
177 in the IMPERIAL strain, which was significantly raised compared to VIENNA 8 ($p = 0.0036^{**}$). In
178 line with the earlier phenotypic stability experiments, the pupal-adult recovery rates were
179 significantly lower in the VIENNA 8 strain, compared to both wild-type and IMPERIAL strains ($p <$
180 0.05^*). Overall egg-adult survival was significantly reduced in VIENNA 8 when assessed against
181 wild-type ($p = 0.0127^*$) and IMPERIAL ($p = 0.0368^*$) strains alike. Egg-adult survival in wild-type
182 and IMPERIAL strains, however, was statistically similar ($p = 0.3274$), indicative of good fitness
183 in the IMPERIAL strain.

184

185 We also explored adult longevity with virgin males and females restricted to separate husbandry
186 under regular lab conditions (Fig. 2C). Highest survival was observed in wild-type females, whilst
187 the shortest longevity belonged to VIENNA 8 females. Pairwise comparisons via log-rank tests
188 were performed between strains, and the combinations of strain and sex (tables S1 and S2).
189 Altogether, VIENNA 8 had significant reductions in longevity compared to both wild-type ($p =$
190 0.0022^{**}) and IMPERIAL ($p = 0.0048^{**}$) strains. Wild-type Benakeion and IMPERIAL strains with
191 the same genetic background, on the other hand, did not have a significant difference between
192 one another ($p = 0.3920$). Amongst females, significant differences were recorded for VIENNA 8
193 against both wild-type ($p < 0.0001^{****}$) and IMPERIAL ($p < 0.0001^{****}$) strains, while male
194 comparisons between strains were statistically insignificant. These results are suggestive of
195 comparable longevity of the males and importantly females from the IMPERIAL strain with wild-
196 type.

197

198 A delay in white-pupaed female development has been documented in the VIENNA 8 strain (40).
199 To determine whether similar issues occur in the males of the IMPERIAL strain because of their
200 white-pupaed phenotype, we compared pupal eclosion times from age-matched egg collections
201 by sex. The development times were significantly different by strain and sex (nested ANOVA, F
202 $= 178.6$, $p < 0.0001^{****}$) (Fig. 2D). The time for wild-type males (mean = 18.60 days) and females
203 (mean = 18.75 days) to reach adulthood were statistically similar to IMPERIAL males (mean =
204 18.51 days) and females (mean = 18.59 days) (table S3). Flies from the VIENNA 8 strain were
205 significantly slower to eclose, with means of 20.11 and 24.00 days for males and females

206 accordingly. Whilst there may be differences in acclimation of the VIENNA 8 to a newer laboratory
207 environment in comparison to the other two strains, there was a significant difference between
208 VIENNA 8 males and females ($p < 0.0001^{****}$), which is absent in both wild-type ($p = 0.94854$)
209 and IMPERIAL ($p = 0.99781$) strains. The observed trends strongly indicate that the IMPERIAL
210 strain does not experience a developmental discrepancy between sexes which is present in the
211 current VIENNA 8 GSS.

212
213 The mating preferences of females towards the IMPERIAL, Benakeion and VIENNA 8 strains
214 were assessed through simultaneous allowing of mating between males from all three strains with
215 females from the irradiation-generated *wp*^{-/-} strain. Due to the recessive nature of the *wp*
216 mutation, the father(s) were easily 'revealed' through pupal colour and corresponding adult
217 phenotype screening (Table 1). The most common parentage belonged to wild-type male(s)
218 (36.93%), followed by equal parentage by IMPERIAL male(s) (28.41%) and VIENNA 8 male(s)
219 (28.41%). We also observed offspring cohorts from single mothers with mixed strain paternity at
220 a low frequency (6.25%). This data indicates that the pupal colour of the IMPERIAL males does
221 not disadvantage their mating success in respect to brown-pupaed VIENNA 8 males.

222
223 Here, we describe an entirely novel CRISPR/Cas9-generated CGSS method with proof of concept
224 for the major agricultural pest *C. capitata* using the *wp* gene involved in pupal pigmentation (16).
225 Although multiple robust next-generation GSS approaches have been established in the medfly
226 to date (24-26, 33), the herein-established IMPERIAL strain is the first to exclusively encompass
227 endogenous elements. Our approach uses the sex-specific intron of *tra*, a gene responsible for
228 female-specific fate induction in the *Tephritidae* fruit fly family and beyond, making it an appealing
229 target for cross-species application (41-42). Importantly, the Y-chromosome-independent GSS
230 approach highlighted herein is time-effective as it only requires comprehensible cross completion
231 for line establishment. Via CRISPR/Cas9-mediated HDR, we integrated the *tra* intron into the *wp*
232 gene to achieve its expression in females exclusively, resulting in a brown-pupae phenotype. Due
233 to sex-specific splicing (fig. S2), males in the strain do not translate *wp* transcripts successfully.
234 Specifically, this is caused by the inclusion of early termination codons upon transcription leading
235 to a white-pupae phenotype. Given that no foreign DNA is inserted into the genome, our approach
236 may be easier to gain regulatory approvals for release, but this remains to be determined.

237
238 Characterisation of the IMPERIAL strain revealed that its fitness is comparative to its ancestral
239 wild-type strain from which it was generated. This included survival during development and upon

240 adulthood, as well as eclosion time comparison between males and females (Fig. 2). Despite
241 statistically similar egg-adult survival, however, the IMPERIAL strain egg hatching rates was
242 insignificantly reduced. In all above-mentioned assessments the VIENNA 8 strain performance
243 indicated greater fitness costs than in the herein generated strain, although mating
244 competitiveness was similar between the two GSSs (Table 1). To explore the fitness of the
245 IMPERIAL strain in further detail, and hence its suitability for SIT implementation, larger scale
246 trials need to be performed. Among all males and females screened in the process of line
247 characterisation in this study, no reverse phenotypes were observed, suggestive of vast line
248 stability. Furthermore, similarly to wild-type flies, the males and females are consistently
249 distributed in equal proportions in the IMPERIAL strain (Fig. 2A). This highlights the limited effect
250 of the white-pupae phenotype on the male survival to adulthood in our GSS, opening a possibility
251 for its efficient facility-based rearing. In theory, the sex-sorting of this strain can be performed at
252 pupal developmental stage using automated machinery, already employed, and optimised at SIT
253 *C. capitata* facilities. Thus, with its stability and cisgenic nature, our system could be an
254 advantageous and cost-effective alternative for currently used strategies in SIT-mediated
255 population control.

256

257 The latest reiteration of the traditional GSSs, VIENNA 8, possesses a heat sensitivity component
258 via the *tsl* gene (15). As its wild-type copy is expressed from the Y-chromosome in an
259 autosomally-mutant *tsl* (*tsl*^{-/-}) background, only males are tolerant to heat (4). To improve our
260 system further, a heat-inducible component can be added to the IMPERIAL strain. This will
261 additionally allow for a thorough investigation of the fitness costs in VIENNA 8 observed in this
262 work. Once *tsl* locus is characterised in full, alternative iterations of the *tra* intron for functional
263 male-specific splicing, or entirely different sex-specific introns (37, 43) can be used for its
264 expression.

265

266 **Data availability**

267 Complete plasmid sequence is available at Addgene.org (#218233). The raw data used for figure
268 generation is provided in the Source data files. The sequencing data are available at NCBI under
269 BioProject PRJNA1189200 (Reviewer link
270 <https://dataview.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/object/PRJNA1189200?reviewer=8am21kg9tm2eskvh6ls27knsd>)
271 The herein-generated knock-in strain is available upon request from A.M.

272

273 **Disclaimer**

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277

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288

289 **Author Contributions**

290 A.M and O.S.A conceived the project and directed the research with contributions from E.B. J.L
291 and N.P.K designed the construct and J.L performed the cloning. A.M and O.S.A designed the
292 experiments. A.M performed the germline transformation. S.D performed medfly and molecular
293 validation experiments. S.D maintained the strains with the help of J.M. S.D, A.M and O.S.A
294 analysed the data. J.L prepared samples for sequencing; I.A performed the sequencing and
295 analysis. All authors contributed to writing and editing of the manuscript and approved the final
296 article.

297

298 **Competing interests**

299 A patent has been filed on this technology. O.S.A is a founder of Agragene, Inc. and Synvect, Inc.
300 with equity interest. N.P.K is a founder of Synvect, Inc. with equity interest. The terms of this
301 arrangement have been reviewed and approved by the University of California, San Diego in
302 accordance with its conflict-of-interest policies. All other authors declare no competing interests.

303

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436

437 **Figure legends**

438 **Fig. 1 Design behind the cisgenic IMPERIAL strain.**

439 (A) A simplified diagram showcasing the IMPERIAL strain generation and its underlying
440 mechanism. The knock-in, mediated via homology-directed repair was performed into the
441 Benakeion wild-type strain. Due to the presence of premature stop codons in the male-specific
442 exons, the males are phenotypically white-pupaed, whilst in females, gene rescue occurs
443 resulting in a brown-pupae phenotype (E1-E4, Exons 1-4; LHA, left homology arm; MFS, Major
444 Facilitator Superfamily; RHA, right homology arm; *tra*, *transformer*; *wp*, *white pupae*). (B) Graphic
445 summary of IMPERIAL strain establishment via outcrosses to the irradiation-generated
446 homozygous recessive *white pupae* mutant (*wp*^{-/-}) strain (KI, knock-in).

447

448 **Fig. 2 Characterisation of the cisgenic IMPERIAL sexing strain.**

449 (A) Stack graphs displaying pupal colour and adult phenotypes in IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8
450 strains for five consecutive generations (F2-F6). Chi-squared test significance levels are indicated
451 as follows: $p < 0.05 = *$, $p < 0.01 = **$, $p < 0.001 = ***$. (B) Bar charts showing egg-adult survival
452 of the IMPERIAL strain compared to both its parental wild-type Benakeion, and VIENNA 8 strains,
453 completed in biological triplicates. Egg-adult survival was measured using 5-hour collections of
454 eggs and their subsequent hatching rates, hatched larval-pupal recovery rates, and pupal-adult
455 recovery rates. Bar levels represent mean values, whilst individual replicate values are shown
456 with dots. Dunn's test significance levels are indicated as follows: $p < 0.05 = *$, $p < 0.01 = **$. (C)
457 Survival curves (Kaplan-Meier) of adult males and females from IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 and wild-
458 type Benakeion strains. The 95% confidence intervals are displayed using pale shading for each
459 test group. (D) Proportion of eclosing males and females from IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 and wild-
460 type Benakeion strains measured daily from age-matched triplicate 24-hour egg collections. Dots
461 represent mean values of the replicates and standard error is indicated using whiskers. (A-D)
462 were constructed in RStudio. Source data is included in the source data file.

463

464 **Table legends**

465 **Table 1 Mating preference of females towards wild-type, IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8 strains.**

466 Males from the three tested strains were collectively released to mate with females from the
467 recessive homozygous *white pupae* mutant (*wp*^{-/-}) strain in 3 repeats. Adult progeny from
468 individual females was scored by pupal colour and corresponding adult phenotypes.

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Supplementary materials

Generating Cisgenic Sexing Strains in Insect Pests

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501

502 **Materials & Methods**

503 **Plasmid design and construction**

504 We used Gibson enzymatic assembly to build the 1167A plasmid, which contains *C. capitata* *MFS*
505 *transporter* Exon 3 (LOC101451947), the *tra* intron and Opie2-DsRed outside the homology arms.
506 A pre-existing plasmid containing *piggyBac* flanks, with an Opie2 promoter regulating DsRed, was
507 linearised by NdeI and KpnI to clone 1167A. The *MFS transporter* Exon3 was amplified into two
508 fragments from *C. capitata* genomic DNA using primer pairs 1167A.c1F and c2R, as well as
509 1167A.c5F and c6R (table S4). The *tra* intron was amplified from 795H1 (Addgene #205482)
510 using primer pair 1167A.c3F and c4R, then inserted inside of the *MFS* exon 3 coding sequence
511 (table S4).

512

513 ***C. capitata* maintenance**

514 All fly stains were reared under standard lab conditions described previously (1). A carrot-based
515 diet was provided for larval development (2) and a 1:1 yeast: glucose mix was given to adult flies.
516 The Benakeion wild-type strain was supplied by the Saccone Lab (University of Naples “Federico
517 II”), whilst irradiation-generated *white pupae* *-/-* (*wp**-/-*) (3) and VIENNA 8 D53- strains were
518 obtained from the FAO/IAEA Centre of Nuclear Techniques in Food and Agriculture (Seibersdorf,
519 Austria).

520

521 ***C. capitata* germline transformation**

522 Microinjections of the 1167A plasmid were performed into embryos of the wild-type Benakeion
523 strain. The plasmid (250 ng/μl) was injected alongside a pre-assembled ribonucleoprotein (RNP)
524 complex of Cas9 protein (200 ng/μl) (PNA Bio) and pre-synthesized gRNA-*wp* (100 ng/μl)
525 (Synthego) (4).

526

527 ***wp*^{KI/+} line establishment**

528 The cross scheme for G0-G3 line generation is summarized in Fig. 1. The injected G0s were
529 reciprocally crossed to the characterised irradiation-generated *wp**-/-* strain (3). The resulting G1
530 progeny was separated by pupal colour, and all males emerging from white pupae were
531 backcrossed in pools to the females from the irradiation-generated *wp**-/-* strain. At G2, the brown
532 pupae were isolated, and all 10 female adults from the same parental G1 cross were collectively
533 crossed to five sibling white-pupaed males. After mating, genomic DNA (gDNA) was individually
534 extracted from G2 brown-pupaed females using an altered phenol-chloroform protocol (5). The

535 knock-in site was amplified using Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix with HF Buffer (New
536 England Biolabs®) with genome-specific 1167A_F and 1167A_R primers (table S4) designed in
537 Geneious Prime 2023.1.2. To confirm the initial integration, the PCR products were purified via
538 Monarch® PCR & DNA Cleanup Kit (New England Biolabs®) and analysed via Oxford Nanopore
539 sequencing (Full Circle Labs).

540

541 Over the course of the following 4 generations (G3-G6) multiple sibling crosses were performed
542 in parallel and the parental genotypes were verified. Hereby three possible alleles were
543 differentiated: 1) the irradiation-generated *wp*^{-/-}; 2) the intron-less *wp*^{-/-} with indels and 3) the *tra*
544 intron knock-in (fig. S5). For this, a multiplex 3-primer PCR was designed using a forward
545 (1167A_F) binding upstream of the integration site, a reverse (1167A_R) downstream of the
546 integration site and a second reverse (8kb_B_R) binding to the irradiation-generated *wp*^{-/-}
547 inserted sequence (fig. S5).

548

549 **Verification of genome integration site in the homozygous strain**

550 To verify the insertion site in the *wp*^{KI/+} IMPERIAL strain, we conducted Oxford Nanopore
551 genomic DNA sequencing. Genomic DNA was extracted from four knock-in adult males and four
552 knock-in adult females using the Blood & Cell Culture DNA Midi Kit (Qiagen).

553

554 **PCR *tra* intron splicing confirmation**

555 In parallel, single males and females were separately collected for gDNA and RNA extractions.
556 gDNA was extracted as detailed above. RNA was extracted via an adapted TRIzol® (Ambion)-
557 chloroform-based protocol (6). cDNA was synthesised from total RNA using Maxima H Minus
558 First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit with dsDNase (ThermoFisher) according to the instructions
559 provided by the manufacturer. Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix with HF Buffer (New
560 England Biolabs®) was used for PCR amplification from gDNA and cDNA templates using the
561 1167_F_V1 splicing and 1167A_R primer pair (table S4). Bands amplified from cDNA of the
562 IMPERIAL strain were purified using a Monarch® DNA Gel Extraction Kit (New England Biolabs®)
563 and Sanger sequenced (Genewiz Inc.). Male cDNA PCR reaction was additionally subjected to
564 Sanger sequencing post-PCR product cloning using the StrataClone PCR Cloning Kit (Agilent)
565 whereby different isoforms were isolated.

566

567 **RNA sequencing**

568 To confirm the sex-specific expression of the *wp* gene, we performed Illumina RNA sequencing.
569 Total RNA was extracted from mature *wp*^{KI/+} adult males and females from the IMPERIAL strain
570 in three biological replicates (six samples) using the miRNeasy Tissue/Cells Advanced Mini Kit
571 (Qiagen), following the manufacturer's protocol. Genomic DNA was removed using the gDNA
572 eliminator column included with the kit. RNA integrity was tested with the RNA 6000 Pico Kit for
573 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies).

574
575 Male (ID# 27026-27028) and female (ID# 27023-27025) libraries with three replicates each were
576 sequenced to approximate depth of 20M paired end reads (table S5). The reads were aligned
577 with STAR (<https://github.com/alexdobin/STAR>) to the EGII-3.2.1 genome assembly
578 (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/genome/GCA_905071925.1/), into which *traF* intron was
579 inserted at the white pupae locus (GCA_905071925.1_EGII-3.2.1_genomic.traF-intron.fna). To
580 generate a more complete annotation file we transferred the Ccap_2.1 annotations
581 (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/genome/GCA_000347755.4/) to the EGII-3.2.1 genome
582 by aligning Ccap_2.1 transcript sequences with BLAT and parsing the alignments to generate a
583 GTF file (Supplemental File 1), which was used for all subsequent analysis steps. Gene
584 abundances were quantified with featureCounts
585 (<https://subread.sourceforge.net/featureCounts.html>), count data (table S6, source data) were
586 converted to TPM (table S7, source data) and FPKM (table S8, source data) values and combined
587 using Perl scripts. Gene annotations were downloaded from EnsemblMetazoa using the BioMart
588 tool (https://metazoa.ensembl.org/Ceratitis_capitata_gca000347755v4/Info/Index) and added to
589 the quantification data (tables S6-S8, source data). TPM values were used to perform PCA and
590 clustering analyses in R to identify possible sample outliers. Replicates for each sex clustered
591 together as expected and displayed high correlations between each other without obvious outliers
592 (Fig. S4, table S9, source data). To visualize splicing of the *traF* intron within the white pupae
593 locus (LOC101451947), BAM files produced by STAR were imported into IGV
594 (<https://igv.org/doc/desktop/>).

595

596 **Stability assay**

597 From G3 until G7 all pupae were separated by colour and corresponding adults were scored by
598 sex. When the homozygosity of the IMPERIAL strain was verified at G7 (F0), alongside the
599 VIENNA 8 D53- strain, for 5 consecutive generations (F2-F6) eggs were collected five days after
600 eclosion and raised under regular conditions until pupal stage of development. Brown and white
601 pupae were then separated, and the sex of all adults from each pool was recorded.

602

603 **Egg-adult survival assay**

604 Sibling crosses of 10 males and 20 females were set up in triplicates simultaneously for the
605 IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 D53-, and wild-type Benakeion strains. Egg numbers and their hatching
606 rates were determined as described previously (7). Specifically, five days after eclosion, all eggs
607 laid within a 5-hour period were collected and unhatched eggs were counted twice four days apart
608 using Fiji (8). Pupal and adult recovery rates were determined thereafter.

609

610 **Adult longevity assay**

611 Age-matched adults from the wild-type Benakeion, IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8 D53- strains were
612 separated by sex upon eclosion and placed into cages of 10 individuals. Three male and three
613 female replicates were set up simultaneously for each strain; and maintained under standard
614 conditions thereafter. Daily, dead flies were counted and removed from the cages for 30
615 consecutive days.

616

617 **Mating-preference assay**

618 90 females from the irradiation-generated *wp*^{-/-} strain (3) were simultaneously placed together
619 with 15 males from each of the Benakeion, IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8 D53- strains for a total of a
620 1:2 male: female ratio. The experiment was repeated 3 times. The flies were left to mate for 4 full
621 days, after which females were separated into individual small cages. Upon oviposition, eggs from
622 all females which oviposited were separately collected and reared normally until pupation. In the
623 cases where white and brown pupae were present, they were separated by colour. Adults
624 eclosing from both mixed and brown pupae-only collections were screened by sex.

625

626 **Eclosion assay**

627 24-hour egg collections were made from sibling crosses of 10 males and 20 females of the
628 IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 D53-, and wild-type Benakeion strains, set up in parallel triplicates. The
629 offspring were reared under normal conditions until pupation, whereby IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8
630 pupae were sorted by colour. The eclosing adults were therein scored by sex every day.

631

632 **Figure generation and statistical analyses**

633 All statistical analysis and plot generation was performed in RStudio. Chi-squared tests were used
634 for sex ratio and pupal colour analysis. Egg-adult survival was assessed using Kruskal-Wallis and
635 Dunn's tests. Longevity data was plotted and analysed using survival and survminer packages.

636 Eclosion rates were assessed using nested ANOVA by strain, with sex added in as an extra factor.
637 Pairwise comparisons were conducted via a *post hoc* Tukey HSD test thereafter. Microsoft
638 PowerPoint and Inkscape 1.3.2 (9) were used to create construct and fly-centred diagrams.

639

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667

668 **Supplementary Figure legends**

669 **Fig. S1 Oxford Nanopore genome sequencing of the *white pupae* genomic site.**

670 Diagrams depicting the nanopore sequencing reads (top grey) aligning to the *white pupae*
671 genomic location (blue) with the *tra* intron inserted in the IMPERIAL strain.

672

673 **Fig. S2 *white pupae* is spliced sex-specifically in the IMPERIAL strain.**

674 (A) The diagram showing the *white pupae* gene in the genome of the *transformer* (*tra*) intron
675 IMPERIAL knock-in (KI) strain with forward and reverse primers labelled as F and R, accordingly
676 (table S4). (B) The annotated electrophoresis gel of the PCR products using primers from (A).
677 The PCR was performed on genomic and complementary DNA templates from wild-type and
678 IMPERIAL adults. The DNA ladder and the negative control were run in the first and tenth wells,
679 respectively.

680

681 **Fig. S3 RNA sequencing alignments to the *wp* genomic locus.**

682 A zoomed-out genome browser view of the *white pupae* genomic locus and gene structure (blue
683 bars on bottom). RNAseq reads were aligned (light grey bars) for the female samples (27023-
684 27025) and the male samples (27026-27028). The inserted *tra* intron is indicated in dotted red
685 box.

686

687 **Fig. S4 Medfly RNAseq Clustering and Principal Component Analysis.**

688

689 **Fig. S5 *white pupae* genotyping for homozygous IMPERIAL strain generation.**

690 Diagrams depicting the genotyping strategy to distinguish the three possible alleles, used at every
691 generation from G2 till G7.

692

693 **Supplementary Table legends**

694 **Table S1 Statistical analysis of adult longevity by strain.**

695 *P*-values for strain-by-strain pairwise log-rank test comparisons for adult longevity with Bonferroni
696 corrections.

697

698 **Table S2 Statistical analysis of adult longevity by strain and sex.**

699 *P*-values for pairwise log-rank test comparisons by sex and strain for adult longevity with
700 Bonferroni corrections.

701

702 **Table S3 Statistical analysis of pupal eclosion times by strain and sex.**

703 *P*-values for pairwise comparisons of *post hoc* Tukey HSD test after nested ANOVA by strain and
704 sex.

705

706 **Table S4 Primer summary.**

707 Sequences of primers used for construct cloning and cisgenic strain characterisation.

Figures

Figure 1

Design behind the cisgenic IMPERIAL strain.

(A) A simplified diagram showcasing the IMPERIAL strain generation and its underlying mechanism. The knock-in, mediated via homology-directed repair was performed into the Benakeion wild-type strain. Due to the presence of premature stop codons in the male-specific exons, the males are phenotypically whitepupaed, whilst in females, gene rescue occurs resulting in a brown-pupae phenotype (E1-E4, Exons 1-4; LHA, left homology arm; MFS, Major Facilitator Superfamily; RHA, right homology arm; tra, transformer; wp, white pupae). (B) Graphic summary of IMPERIAL strain establishment via outcrosses to the irradiation generated homozygous recessive white pupae mutant ($wp^{-/-}$) strain (KI, knock-in).

Figure 2

Characterisation of the cisgenic IMPERIAL sexing strain.

(A) Stack graphs displaying pupal colour and adult phenotypes in IMPERIAL and VIENNA 8 strains for five consecutive generations (F2-F6). Chi-squared test significance levels are indicated as follows: $p < 0.05 = *$, $p < 0.01 = **$, $p < 0.001 = ***$. (B) Bar charts showing egg-adult survival of the IMPERIAL strain compared to both its parental wild-type Benakeion, and VIENNA 8 strains, completed in biological triplicates. Egg-adult survival was measured using 5-hour collections of eggs and their subsequent hatching rates, hatched larval-pupal recovery rates, and pupal-adult recovery rates. Bar levels represent mean values, whilst individual replicate values are shown with dots. Dunn's test significance levels are indicated as follows: $p < 0.05 = *$, $p < 0.01 = **$. (C) Survival curves (Kaplan-Meier) of adult males and females from IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 and wild-type Benakeion strains. The 95% confidence intervals are displayed using pale shading for each test group. (D) Proportion of eclosing males and females from IMPERIAL, VIENNA 8 and wild-type Benakeion strains measured daily from age-matched triplicate 24-hour egg collections. Dots represent mean values of the replicates and standard error is indicated using whiskers. (A-D) were constructed in RStudio. Source data is included in the source data file.

Supplementary Files

This is a list of supplementary files associated with this preprint. Click to download.

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- [supplementarymaterials.pdf](#)